

ACCEPTABILITY AND MARKETABILITY OF KAPILINGKA BAR COOKIES

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Acceptability and Marketability of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of acceptability and marketability of Kamias, Pili and Langka (KaPilingka) bar cookies in 30 grams, 60 grams and 90 grams proportions as evaluated by sellers, consumers and pasalubong store owners during the school year 2023 – 2024. The study employed an experimental research method which aimed to determine the acceptability and marketability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in three different proportions. The statistical treatment used in this study are the weighted mean, analysis of variance and the Tukey pairwise comparison. Based on the findings, the three groups of respondents evaluated the level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30g, 60g, and 90g proportion as Very Acceptable. In addition, for 30g and 60g proportions, there were significant differences on the evaluation of the respondents on the level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka, while there were no significant differences on 90g proportion. Meanwhile, as regards the level of marketability of the product, the respondents evaluated the 30g, 60g, and 90g proportions as Highly Marketable. Moreover, there were significant difference on the evaluation on the level of marketability of the product in 30g and 60g proportions, while there were no significant differences in term of 90g proportion. The Consumer, Sellers and Pasalubong Store Owner respondents gave comments and suggestions for the improvement of the KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies.

Keywords: *acceptability, marketability, bar cookies*

Introduction

The process of accepting or rejecting food has many facets. Levels of food acceptance vary among people in various groups, as well as among the same people in various eras and situations. Simply put, the level of consumer participation at any one time is highly correlated with the acceptability of the cuisine. The fundamental standards that determine whether food is acceptable are sensory attributes that consumers look for in their meals. Two more key factors that have an immediate impact on food are consumer characteristics and food enjoyment.

According to Sinesio et al. (2018) the expectations that customers have for a certain product and their acceptance of it are closely related. Customers frequently make comparisons between the actual qualities of a product and their expectations regarding its sensory qualities. Consumers pay attention to how the product's flavor matches the advertisement's description, how it performs in relation to the manufacturer's stated specifications, and how the product actually compares to the label on the package.

More so, Kostyra et al. (2018) opined that upon ultimately consuming food products and experiencing their sensory attributes, consumers are empowered to make an informed decision regarding their likeness or distaste for the product. It is therefore crucial for food producers to maximize the sensory features that customers perceive of a given product. Taste, scent, texture, and appearance of food all specifically influence the decision that a consumer makes on the preference of food substance. This raises the product's perceived worth among different customers in a direct manner. Before, during, and after eating, the aroma, taste, texture, and sight of food all serve as important sensory cues. These characteristics point customers in the direction of the food source, their preferences, their choice, and their level of satisfaction after eating.

On the other hand, fruits are a great addition to baked goods like cookies, not only for their delicious taste but also for their nutritional value. Incorporating fruits into cookie recipes can increase the fiber content, vitamins, and antioxidants. It can be a tremendous aid to the community to enjoy traditional comfort food with the same high nutritional content and health advantages given the rising demand for innovations and the heightened health challenges.

Pimentel (2022) stated that the fruits, leaves, and stems of the kamias or bilimbi tree are rich in vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, among other health advantages. Its antimicrobial and antidiabetic fruits are noteworthy, despite their lesser popularity. Backyards are where kamias are found in the Philippines. There are numerous culinary applications for kamias in Asian cuisines. It can be eaten raw, dipped in sugar, salt, or soy sauce, or juiced, savored, or pickled. It is added to common dishes like paksiw and sinigang as a souring agent. It is well known that kamias lowers blood sugar.

Likewise, Del Coro (2020) stipulated that Pili nuts are a good source of zinc, iron, calcium, potassium, and other B-vitamins in addition to a wide range of other vitamins and minerals. They are particularly high in vitamin E, copper, thiamin, manganese, magnesium, and phosphorus. Because the natural oil in the nuts allows for maximum absorption, a 30-gram serving of roasted, unsalted pili nuts supplies 60–70% of the recommended daily intake of Vitamin E. Apart from their elevated fat content, they exhibit elevated levels of Vitamin E, thiamin, phosphorous, manganese, and magnesium in contrast to other nuts. Furthermore, they possess all the necessary amino acids to constitute a comprehensive protein supply, which sets them apart from other nuts. Numerous additional minerals, such as potassium, copper, zinc, calcium, and iron, can also be found in them.

With the above cited preliminary articles, incorporating fruits into cookie recipes can increase the nutritional value and improve the sensory quality of cookies. However, it's important to consider the moisture content of the fruit and adjust the recipe accordingly to ensure proper texture and shelf life. The present research then aims to explore the acceptability and marketability of cookies made of Kamias fruit, Pili nuts, and powdered Langka seeds as ingredients of KaPilingka bar cookies. Personally, the researcher wants to have a food business that would highlight on baked products. Overall, this study has the potential to contribute to the development of new and novel food products that give extra health benefits to consumers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of acceptability and marketability of Kamias, Pili and Langka (KaPilingka) bar cookies in 30 grams, 60 grams and 90grams proportions as evaluated by sellers, consumers and pasalubong store owners during the school year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What was the physicochemical analysis of the prepared KaPiliNgka bar cookies in terms of the following aspects:
 - 1.1. carbohydrates;
 - 1.2. fats;
 - 1.3. pH level;
 - 1.4. protein; and
 - 1.5. moisture content?
2. What was the level of acceptability of KaPilingka bar cookies in three proportions as evaluated by sellers, consumers and pasalubong store owner respondents in terms of the following criteria?
 - 2.1. appearance;
 - 2.2. color;
 - 2.3. aroma;
 - 2.4. taste; and
 - 2.5. texture?
3. Were there significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of KaPilingka bar cookies in terms of the above-cited criteria?
4. What was the evaluation of the sellers, consumers and pasalubong store owner respondents on the level of marketability of KaPilingka bar cookies in three proportions in terms of the following aspects?
 - 4.1. consumer's demand;
 - 4.2. product competitiveness;
 - 4.3. production cost;
 - 4.4. packaging and branding; and
 - 4.5. distribution channels?
5. Were there significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of KaPilingka bar cookies in three proportions in terms of the above cited aspects?
6. What were the comments and suggestions offered by the three groups of respondents to further improve the product?

Literature Review

Momsotherside (2021) on her article on "Health Benefits of Bilimbi Fruit or Kamias and A Must Try-recipe" stated that in comparison to the flavor of calamansi (lime), bilimbi fruit is small, green, and sour. Five to ten meters is the maximum height of the bilimbi tree. The leaves range in length from 3 to 6 cm, and the trunk is short. The fruit is used as a component in curries, soups, juice, sauces, pickles, and other dishes. It is referred to as kamias in our nation.

As stipulated by Merano (2018) in the article entitled: "Benefits of Kamias On Your Health", although kamias is not as well-known as other tropical fruits, it is quickly becoming so in many nations. Its nutritional and therapeutic worth is well known to Asian nations and islands, particularly the Philippines. The balimbing, or star fruit, and the kamias fruit, sometimes known as bilimbi, are closely related. However, it has a sour flavor that many employ as a culinary element, unlike star fruit. In many countries, the primary purpose of kamias is for food preparation. Its sour flesh is adaptable enough for many cooks to utilize as a basis or component in a variety of cuisines. In addition to being adaptable, kamias is nutrient rich.

Furthermore, Link (2020) stated in the article "Pili Nuts: The Keto-Friendly Nuts that Support the Heart and Bones" that there are numerous reasons to think about include pili nuts in your diet. These are a handful of the nuts' many health advantages. 1) Excellent Source of Nutritious Fats. Pili nuts contain about 23 grams of heart-healthy fat in only one ounce of food. Monounsaturated fats, which have been demonstrated to reduce inflammation and hence aid in the prevention of chronic disease, make up most of their composition.

Relatively, Migala (2020) stated that pili nuts are rich in other nutrients besides fat. This was mentioned in the article "What Are Pili Nuts—and Are They Good for You?" In particular, a one-ounce portion will provide you with a decent supply of minerals like manganese, which is good for bones, and magnesium, which is involved in blood sugar and glucose function. It will also provide you with nutrients like copper and the B vitamin thiamin, which are important for energy metabolism and production.

De Jesus and Gamis (2021) opined that a new moist cake made from pili pulp and nuts has been added to the vast list of pili-based goods. The pili pulp was only used as the primary ingredient by a small number of product developers. Consequently, the product was rated as "liked very much" by 118 respondents, and as "liked somewhat" by 18 respondents. With a 7.91 total acceptance, this is a very favorable result. Additionally, as introduction items for the public, laboratory batch samples were created.

Lastly, Maskey et al. (2020) sought to determine how the addition of jackfruit seed flour affects the cookie's quality. Cookies made with jackfruit seed flour have considerably ($p < 0.05$) higher protein, fat, fiber, and ash levels than cookies made with wheat flour (control). Also, it was discovered that the phytate and oxalate contents were considerably ($p < 0.05$) greater in the cookies made with jackfruit seed flour than in the control group, but they were below the tolerance level and safe to eat.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used an experimental method to determine the acceptability and marketability of kamias fruit (*Averrhoa bilimbi*), pili nuts (*Canarium ovatum*) and langka seed (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) powdered as ingredients in making kapilingka Cookies. According to Sirisilla (2023) An experimental approach to doing experimental research using two sets of variables is achieved through the use of experimental research design, which is a framework of protocols and procedures.

Respondents

This study was conducted in Marikina City, Metro Manila, Philippines for the school year 2023-2024. The data obtained for the process of investigation were from 90 overall respondents from the said area. These people have been randomly selected to evaluate the acceptability, and marketability of kamias, pili, and langka seeds. Purposive sampling was utilized in this study since the respondents possess the same characteristics that answers the study.

Instruments

A survey questionnaire was employed as the data collection tool in this investigation. This would constitute the assessment of the three respondents' groups for the degree of marketability and acceptability of the powdered Langka seed, Pili nuts, and Kamias fruit.

Additionally, with the help of a nine-point hedonic scale, the criteria in terms of Taste, Flavor, Texture, Aroma and Color are meant to be defined. Part I is the respondents' level of acceptability of Kamias Fruit, Pili Nuts, and Langka seed powder as main ingredients of Kapilingka Bar Cookies.

Part II of the survey questionnaire is the respondents' level of marketability along the five components such as consumer demand, promotability, supply availability and sustainability. Additionally, with the help of a nine-point hedonic rating scale, the criteria in terms of appearance, aroma, color, texture and taste are meant to be defined. The survey instrument on the other hand was revalidated by field experts.

Procedure

The researcher started the data collection process by creating the survey questions. The researcher took sure to include questions that are actually pertinent to the topic and issue of the study in order to ensure its legitimacy. Furthermore, the presence of survey questionnaires was administered to the 90 mentioned respondents from Marikina City by the researcher with its secured letter of permissions from the Local government Unit (LGU) and was signed by the office in charge. After the administration and collection of the questionnaires, the researcher tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the results with the use of appropriate statistical tools needed to reach a certain result.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher himself explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. He ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Physicochemical Analysis of the Prepared KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies

The moisture content of 100 g KaPiliNgka bar cookies using the tested method of vacuum oven drying resulted in 16.1. The fat with the same unit was applied through acid hydrolysis and mojonner extraction, which resulted in 23.0. The protein content of the product has been measured at 5.84 through the Kjeldahl test method. Hence, the carbohydrates of the KaPiliNgka bar cookies have a 53.4 result by the use of the computation method. However, the pH with its 50% dispersion had results of 4.86 at 24.4 oC tested through electrometry.

Table 1. *Physicochemical Analysis of the Prepared KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies*

Parameters	Unit	Test Method	Results
Moisture	g/100 g	Vacuum Oven Drying	16.1
Fat	g/100 g	Acid Hydrolysis – Mojonnier Extraction	23.0
Ash	g/100 g	Ignition – Gravimetry	1.62
Protein (N x 6.25)	g/100 g	Kjeldahl	5.84
Carbohydrates	g/100 g	By Computation	53.4
pH (50% Dispersion)		Electrometry	4.86 @ 24.4 °C

Level of Acceptability of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in Three Proportions as Evaluated by Sellers, Consumers and Pasalubong Store Owner

Table 2. *Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion as to Appearance*

The appearance of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is look appetizing.	8.77	EA	8.70	EA	8.77	EA
2. is visually distinctive.	8.00	VA	8.47	VA	8.30	VA
3. have an appealing outward appearance.	8.03	VA	8.40	VA	8.40	VA
4. has an appealing shape.	8.00	VA	8.47	VA	8.40	VA
5. is in excellent shape.	8.07	VA	8.43	VA	8.43	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.17	VA	8.49	VA	8.46	VA

As seen in the table, the three groups of respondents’ evaluation on the level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30 grams proportion as to appearance were descriptively rated as “Very Acceptable” as shown by the overall weighted means of 8.17 for sellers, 8.49 consumers and 8.46 for pasalubong store owners respectively.

This suggests that in the aspect of appearance, the KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30-gram proportion are well-intentioned of being acknowledged and have a good-looking characteristic. Thus, the appetizing look, distinctiveness, and shape of the product were very attractive to the respondents as well.

Table 3. *Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion as to Color*

The color of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is consistent.	8.97	EA	8.83	EA	8.70	EA
2. are appealing and delectable.	8.27	VA	8.40	VA	8.53	EA
3. has a pale bronzy tint.	7.97	VA	8.23	VA	8.33	VA
4. has the hue that can currently be observed on Kamias, Pili and Langka.	8.03	VA	8.33	VA	8.20	VA
5. has a rich color that is quite enticing.	7.93	VA	8.30	VA	8.27	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.23	VA	8.42	VA	8.41	VA

It can be noted from the table that the three groups of respondents’ evaluation on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30 grams proportion as to color were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA), as shown by the overall weighted means of 8.23 for sellers, 8.42 for consumers, and 8.41 for pasalubong store owners. This infers that, as far as color is concerned, the acceptability level of the product plays a significant part in the evaluation of food. Together with texture and flavor, color is measured by food scientists to be a major eminence feature in food where KaPiliNgka bar cookies have possessed such qualities which made the respondents’ evaluation resulted to a very tolerable.

Table 4. *Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion as to Aroma*

The aroma of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has pleasant scent.	8.70	EA	8.67	EA	8.83	EA
2. are buttery in scent.	8.17	VA	8.23	VA	8.40	VA
3. is unremarkable.	8.07	VA	8.40	VA	8.63	EA
4. smells sweet and delicate.	8.13	VA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
5. have a freshy- baked scent.	8.00	VA	8.43	VA	8.47	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.21	VA	8.45	VA	8.58	EA

As shown in table 4, the sellers and consumer respondents have the same evaluation on the acceptability level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30 grams proportion as to aroma, as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.21 for sellers, 8.45 for consumers, which were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA). However, the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30 grams proportion as evaluated by the pasalubong store owners was descriptively rated as "Extremely Agreeable" as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.58.

This indicates that since the product is a key sensory signal and a fundamental component of flavor evaluation, it affects how responders rate flavors and textures. The aroma alerts the respondent to the food's presence before they even notice it.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion as to Taste

The taste of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is delicious and buttery.	8.87	EA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
2. has a flavor that lingers.	8.03	VA	8.33	VA	8.30	VA
3. has a pleasing and pleasurable flavor.	8.23	VA	8.40	VA	8.17	VA
4. is enjoyable to consume.	8.20	VA	8.40	VA	8.20	VA
5. is well-balanced.	8.20	VA	8.37	VA	8.27	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.31	VA	8.41	VA	8.30	VA

As noted in the table, the three groups of respondents' evaluations on the acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30 grams proportion as to taste were the same, which was descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA), as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.31 for sellers, 8.41 for consumers, and 8.30 for pasalubong store owners, respectively. This demonstrates that the respondents find the product's (KaPiliNgka bar cookies) flavor to be intriguing since it produces an engaging respondents' experience that will persuade customers to purchase the product repeatedly.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion as to Texture

The texture of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is only marginally moist.	8.80	EA	8.80	EA	8.23	VA
2. is crunchy and delicious.	8.10	VA	8.13	VA	8.23	VA
3. is flaky.	8.13	VA	8.27	VA	8.47	VA
4. is free of cracks.	8.23	VA	8.37	VA	8.53	EA
5. is gooey.	8.17	VA	8.33	VA	8.23	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.29	VA	8.38	VA	8.34	VA

It can be noted in the table that the three groups of respondents' evaluations acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30 grams proportion as to taste were the same as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.29 for sellers, 8.36 for consumers and 8.34 for pasalubong store owners which were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable". This suggests that the respondents value food texture as a distinguishing characteristic and that this perception may contribute to their high level of meal acceptance.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

The appearance of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is look appetizing.	8.83	EA	8.70	EA	8.67	EA
2. is visually distinctive.	8.50	EA	8.53	EA	8.40	VA
3. have an appealing outward appearance.	8.10	VA	8.27	VA	8.23	VA
4. has an appealing shape.	8.10	VA	8.23	VA	8.17	VA
5. is in excellent shape.	8.20	VA	8.43	VA	8.20	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.35	VA	8.43	VA	8.33	VA

It can be gleaned in the table that the respondents' evaluation on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 60- gram proportion as to appearance were the same, as shown by the overall weighted mean of 8.35 for sellers, 8.43 for consumers, and 8.33 for pasalubong store owners, which were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA). This indicates that the superficially of the above cited product is appealing to the standard of the three groups of respondents in appraising KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 60 grams proportion.

As noted in table 8, the evaluation of the sellers and store owner respondents on the acceptability level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka

bar cookies in 60-gram proportion as to color was the same, as indicated by the overall weighted mean of 8.23 for sellers and 8.47 for store owners, which was descriptively rated as “Very Acceptable” (VA). However, the evaluation of the consumer respondents was descriptively rated as “Extremely Acceptable” (EA) as indicated by the overall weighted mean of 8.50, respectively.

Table 8. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion as to Color

The color of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is consistent.	8.90	EA	8.87	EA	8.70	EA
2. are appealing and delectable.	8.00	VA	8.50	EA	8.33	VA
3. has a pale bronzy tint.	8.03	VA	8.37	VA	8.47	VA
4. has the hue that can currently be observed on Kamias, Pili and Langka.	8.00	VA	8.33	VA	8.27	VA
5. has a rich color that is quite enticing.	8.20	VA	8.43	VA	8.60	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.23	VA	8.50	EA	8.47	VA

This finding suggests that the majority of respondents were certain that the KaPiliNgka bar cookies in a 60-gram proportion seemed to be very enduring as far as color is concerned, as directed by their level of assessment of the said bar cookies. Thus, consistency, hue and enticingly rich color have observed in the new innovated product.

Table 9. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

The aroma of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has pleasant scent.	8.87	EA	8.70	EA	8.67	EA
2. are buttery in scent.	8.30	VA	8.50	EA	8.53	EA
3. is unremarkable.	8.43	VA	8.47	VA	8.53	EA
4. smells sweet and delicate.	8.03	VA	8.47	VA	8.57	EA
5. have a freshy- baked scent.	8.43	VA	8.57	EA	8.60	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.41	VA	8.54	EA	8.58	EA

As noted in the table, the evaluation of the consumer and store owner respondents on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in a 60-gram proportion as to aroma was the similar, as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.54 for consumers and 8.58 for store owners, which was descriptively rated as "Extremely Acceptable" (EA). However, the evaluation of the seller respondents was descriptively rated as “Very Acceptable” as indicated by the overall weighted mean of 8.41 respectively. This finding indicates that the majority of the respondents have the belief that, as far as aroma is concerned, KaPiliNgka bar cookies in a 60-gram proportion appeared to be very admissible, as stressed by their observation and certainty on the above-cited product.

Table 10. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion as to Taste

The taste of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is delicious and buttery.	8.83	EA	8.57	EA	8.70	EA
2. has a flavor that lingers.	8.27	VA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
3. has a pleasing and pleasurable flavor.	8.37	VA	8.37	VA	8.33	VA
4. in enjoyable to consume.	8.43	VA	8.43	VA	8.53	EA
5. is well-balanced.	8.30	VA	8.43	VA	8.23	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.44	VA	8.47	VA	8.47	VA

As shown in the table, the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 60-gram proportion as to taste was the same, as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.44 for sellers, 8.47 for consumers and store owners, which was descriptively rated as “Very Acceptable” (VA). According to this finding, most respondents thought the combination of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in a 60-gram proportion seemed to be extremely acceptable in terms of flavor.

As noted in table 11, the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on of the level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 60-gram proportion as to texture was the similar, as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.30 for sellers, 8.45 for consumers, and 8.38 for store owners, which was descriptively rated as “Very Acceptable” (VA). This result shows that the respondents thought a food's texture was an important characteristic, which may explain why a product is so well-liked. However, it has also been shown that before the product's apparent high degree of popularity, respondents had higher texture development. As a result, the research informants have observed the product's crunchiness, gooeyness, and flakiness.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion as to Texture

The texture of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is only marginally moist.	8.67	EA	8.80	EA	8.33	VA
2. is crunchy and delicious.	8.20	VA	8.23	VA	8.53	EA
3. is flaky.	8.13	VA	8.33	VA	8.23	VA
4. is free of cracks.	8.40	VA	8.50	EA	8.67	EA
5. is gooey.	8.10	VA	8.37	VA	8.13	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.30	VA	8.45	VA	8.38	VA

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

The appearance of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is look appetizing.	8.93	EA	8.53	EA	8.37	VA
2. is visually distinctive.	8.13	EA	8.30	VA	8.00	VA
3. have an appealing outward appearance.	8.13	VA	8.20	VA	8.23	VA
4. has an appealing shape.	8.17	VA	8.43	VA	8.07	VA
5. is in excellent shape.	8.20	VA	8.27	VA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.31	VA	8.35	VA	8.19	VA

As seen in the table, the three groups of respondents' evaluations on the level of acceptability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 90-gram proportion as to appearance were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA), as showed by the overall weighted mean of 8.31 for sellers, 8.35 for consumers, and 8.19 for pasalubong store owners. As a result, the respondents themselves thought that the product had a very tempting, tasty, distinctive, appealing, and wonderful shape.

Table 13. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion as to Color

The color of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is consistent.	9.00	EA	8.67	EA	8.67	EA
2. are appealing and delectable.	8.27	VA	8.23	VA	8.17	VA
3. has a pale bronzy tint.	8.43	VA	8.33	VA	8.47	VA
4. has the hue that can currently be observed on Kamias, Pili and Langka.	8.17	VA	8.20	VA	8.33	VA
5. has a rich color that is quite enticing.	8.37	VA	8.27	VA	8.50	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.45	VA	8.34	VA	8.43	VA

As shown in the table, the three groups of respondents' evaluation on the acceptability level KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 90-gram proportion as to color were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA), as indicated by the overall weighted mean of 8.45 for sellers, 8.34 for consumers, and 8.43 for pasalubong store owners. This suggests that color is important to taste and food assessment in terms of how it affects a product's level of acceptability. The three groups of respondents concur that, along with flavor and product quality, color is one of the three key elements of food quality where the KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 90-gram proportion have possessed such aspects.

Table 14. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

The aroma of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has pleasant scent.	8.70	EA	8.70	EA	8.60	EA
2. are buttery in scent.	8.33	VA	8.30	VA	8.50	EA
3. is unremarkable.	8.47	VA	8.40	VA	8.70	EA
4. smells sweet and delicate.	8.20	VA	8.40	VA	8.47	VA
5. have a freshy- baked scent.	8.40	VA	8.43	VA	8.63	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.42	VA	8.45	VA	8.58	EA

As shown in the table, the sellers and consumers have the same evaluation on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 90-gram proportion as to aroma, as specified by the overall weighted means of 8.42 and 8.45, which were descriptively rated as "Very

Acceptable" (VA), respectively, while the evaluation of the pasalubong store owners was descriptive rated as 8.58 which was descriptively rated as "Extremely Acceptable". According to the finding, the product has an impact on how respondents estimate flavors and attributes because it is a crucial sensory signal and essential part of flavor evaluation. Before the respondent even notices the product, the aroma informs them to its presence.

Table 15. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion as to Taste

The taste of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is delicious and buttery.	8.93	EA	8.57	EA	8.53	EA
2. has a flavor that lingers.	8.23	VA	8.30	VA	8.03	VA
3. has a pleasing and pleasurable flavor.	8.30	VA	8.13	VA	8.27	VA
4. in enjoyable to consume.	8.10	VA	8.17	VA	8.13	VA
5. is well-balanced.	8.33	VA	8.40	VA	8.37	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.38	VA	8.31	VA	8.27	VA

As noted in the table, the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 90-gram proportion as to taste were the same, as directed by the overall weighted mean of 8.38 for sellers, 8.31 for consumers, and 8.27 for pasalubong store owners, which were descriptively rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA). This shows that the 90-gram KaPiliNgka bar cookies were observed by the respondents as having a very acceptable savor. They are also very attractive or pleasant to them in terms of flavor and tastiness, which also encourages a well-balanced taste evaluation, as seen by their level of evaluation of the bar cookies.

Table 16. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion as to Texture

The texture of KaPiliNgka bar cookies...	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is only marginally moist.	8.83	EA	8.53	EA	8.27	VA
2. is crunchy and delicious.	8.20	VA	7.80	VA	8.03	VA
3. is flaky.	8.33	VA	8.10	VA	8.10	VA
4. is free of cracks.	8.20	VA	8.03	VA	7.63	VA
5. is gooev.	8.33	VA	8.30	VA	8.07	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.38	VA	8.15	VA	8.02	VA

It can be gleaned in the table that the three groups of respondents' evaluations on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 90-gram proportion as to taste were the same, as directed by the overall weighted means of 8.38 for sellers, 8.15 for consumers, and 8.02 for pasalubong store owners which were descriptive rated as "Very Acceptable" (VA). This result shows that respondents believed that a food's texture was an essential component of the product, which may explain why they found the KaPiliNgka bar cookies in the 90-gram proportion to be particularly alluring. Adults also had higher texture development prior to the product's apparent high degree of acceptability, it was demonstrated. Because of this, product creation must take into account the crunchiness, flakiness, texture, and gooeyness of the final product.

Test of Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies

Table 17. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in 30 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	6.37	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Color	2.20	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Aroma	4.25	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Taste	0.57	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	0.37	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

The respondents' assessments of the acceptability level of the 30-gram portion of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in terms of color, taste, and texture from sellers, customers, and store owners do not significantly differ from the corresponding computed F values, which are less than the critical F value. With the exception of look and scent, the respondents' assessments are therefore similar.

The table 18 indicates that there are no significant differences between the respondents' assessments of the acceptability level of 60 grams of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture from sellers, customers, and store owners, and the corresponding computed F values, which are less than the critical F value. This suggests that, except for color, the respondents' assessments are similar.

Table 18. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in 60 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.56	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
b. Color	5.70	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
c. Aroma	1.07	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
d. Taste	0.06	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
e. Texture	0.70	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

Table 19. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in 90 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.42	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
b. Color	0.18	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
c. Aroma	1.01	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
d. Taste	0.25	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
e. Texture	2.63	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

The evaluations of the sellers, consumers, and store owner respondents on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 90 grams proportion in terms of appearance, color, aroma, taste and texture do not imply significant differences with the particularly computed F values which are smaller than the critical F value. Hence, the respondents' evaluations are the same.

Evaluation of the Sellers, Consumers and Pasalubong Store Owner Respondents on the Level of Marketability of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in Three Proportions

The overall weighted mean of 4.30 indicates that seller respondents' assessments of the marketability level of 30 grams of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in relation to consumer demand were descriptively classified as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as shown in the next table. Meanwhile, the consumer and pasalubong store owner respondents' evaluation were descriptively rated as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.55 and 4.61 respectively. As a result, they believe that customer requests are reasonable. But in contrast to what the sellers said, there was less of a requirement for the product to be valued by customer demand, and the market was more likely to benefit from its marketability based on consumer demand.

Table 20. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion regarding Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is capable of supplying the need of potential customers.	4.90	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.93	VHM
2. The product's nutritive content allows it to satiate the requirements and desires of potential customers.	4.23	HM	4.50	VHM	4.47	HM
3. The product can be obtained for less than the other comparable high-end brands.	4.23	HM	4.40	HM	4.47	HM
4. Potential customers of various ages can purchase the merchandise.	4.07	HM	4.47	HM	4.57	VHM
5. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.07	HM	4.50	VHM	4.60	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HM	4.55	VHM	4.61	VHM

Table 21. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion regarding Product Competitiveness

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product offers competitive price.	4.73	VHM	4.60	VHM	4.67	VHM
2. The product is one- of-a-kind.	4.20	HM	4.63	VHM	4.43	HM
3. The product offers competitive price range.	4.10	HM	4.40	HM	4.63	VHM
4. There are many well- informed buyers of the product.	4.17	HM	4.60	VHM	4.73	VHM
5. The product can sustain continuous supply and demand of the market.	4.17	HM	4.33	HM	4.63	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.27	HM	4.51	VHM	4.62	VHM

It can be noted in the table that the seller respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 30 grams proportion regarding product competitiveness were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 4.27. Meanwhile, the consumer and pasalubong store owner respondents' evaluation were descriptively rated as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.51 and 4.62 respectively. This means that the KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30g are very easy to market because of its quality and affordable price. Hence, the product sustained and meet the demand of its consumers.

Table 22. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion regarding Product Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is reasonably priced based on cost.	4.93	VHM	4.73	VHM	4.83	VHM
2. The price is affordable.	4.23	HM	4.43	HM	4.63	VHM
3. The amount is based on product's value.	3.80	HM	4.20	HM	4.30	HM
4. The price is suitable to the product's worth.	4.03	HM	4.47	HM	4.57	VHM
5. The price is budget- friendly.	4.13	HM	4.33	HM	4.50	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.23	HM	4.43	HM	4.57	VHM

It can be seen in the table, that the seller and consumer respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 30 grams proportion regarding product cost were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 4.32 for sellers and 4.43 for consumers, while the pasalubong store owners evaluated the level of marketability of the product as Very Highly Marketable with the obtained mean of 4.57.

This indicates that the said bar cookies are competitive in the aspect of its cost where the respondents have evaluated to be saleable. Budget friendly and suitable to the worth of the product which made pleasing to the entire market.

Table 23. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion regarding Packaging and Branding

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The brand name is unique.	4.70	VHM	4.83	VHM	4.87	VHM
2. The packaging visually appealing.	4.27	HM	4.63	VHM	4.60	VHM
3. The product maintains freshness with its resealable top.	4.17	HM	4.47	HM	4.47	HM
4. The product appears original among another cookie products.	4.37	HM	4.63	VHM	4.50	VHM
5. The style of the packaging contains appropriate cushioning.	4.00	HM	4.43	HM	4.43	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HM	4.60	VHM	4.57	VHM

The table shows that the overall weighted mean of 4.30 indicates that the seller respondents' assessments of the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 30 grams proportion regarding packaging and baking were descriptively classified as "Highly Marketable" (HM), while the evaluation of the consumers and pasalubong store owners were descriptively rated as Very Highly Marketable as indicated in the obtained mean of 4.60 and 4.57 respectively. This result indicates that as far as packaging and branding is concerned, attractiveness in the package have added significant value to the product. Thus, this inspired more sales and improved brand awareness.

Table 24. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 30 Grams Proportion regarding Distribution Channels

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can offer potential partnership	4.83	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.80	VHM
2. The product can deliver the opportunity to reach more people and expand awareness.	4.00	HM	4.50	VHM	4.57	VHM
3. The product provides market information to producers.	4.23	HM	4.43	HM	4.50	VHM
4. The product can be easily distributed.	4.07	HM	4.57	VHM	4.60	VHM
5. The product can easily establish goals, service, and reporting requirements.	4.33	HM	4.70	VHM	4.80	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.29	HM	4.61	VHM	4.65	VHM

The table illustrates that the seller respondents' assessments of the marketability level of 30 grams of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in relation to distribution channels were descriptively assessed as “Highly Marketable” (HM), as indicated by the weighted average of 4.29 overall. The results indicate that the KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 30 grams of proportion regarding distribution channels were deemed very highly marketable (VHM) by both pasalubong store owners and consumers. This is supported by the overall weighted means of 4.61 and 4.65, respectively.

Table 25. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion regarding Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is capable of supplying the need of potential customers.	4.80	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.73	VHM
2. The product's nutritive content allows it to satiate the requirements of potential customers.	4.10	HM	4.43	HM	4.40	HM
3. The product can be obtained for less than the other comparable high-end brands.	4.20	HM	4.53	VHM	4.57	VHM
4. Potential customers of various ages can purchase the merchandise.	4.13	HM	4.40	HM	4.53	VHM
5. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.27	HM	4.43	HM	4.53	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HM	4.53	VHM	4.55	VHM

The table provides insight into the seller respondents' assessments of the marketability level of 60-gram KaPiliNgka bar cookies in relation to customer demand. The overall weighted mean of 4.30 indicates that the sellers assessed the product as "Highly Marketable" (HM), while consumers and pasalubong store owners' assessment were descriptively rated as Very Highly Marketable as indicated with the mean of 4.53 and 4.55. These findings demonstrate that the respondents believe that the product can meet the needs of future customers and that it has an organic mechanism that could provide nutritional benefits. They therefore consider customer requests to be reasonable.

Table 26. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion regarding Product Competitiveness

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product offers competitive price.	4.87	VHM	4.73	VHM	4.83	VHM
2. The product is one- of-a-kind.	4.03	HM	4.27	HM	4.20	HM
3. The product offers competitive price range.	4.20	HM	4.37	HM	4.50	VHM
4. There are many well-informed buyers of the product.	4.17	HM	4.40	HM	4.37	HM
5. The product can sustain continuous supply and demand of the market.	4.33	HM	4.67	VHM	4.40	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.32	HM	4.49	HM	4.46	HM

It can be seen in the table that the respondents' assessment on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 60 grams proportion regarding product competitiveness were descriptively rated as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) as evidenced by the means of 4.32 for sellers, 4.49 for consumers and 4.46 for pasalubong store owners. This indicates that due to their high quality and reasonable pricing, the 60g KaPiliNgka bar cookies are very simple to market.

Table 27. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion regarding Product Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is reasonably priced based on cost.	4.70	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.83	VHM
2. The price is affordable.	3.93	HM	4.57	VHM	4.47	HM
3. The amount is based on product's value.	4.13	HM	4.47	HM	4.43	HM
4. The price is suitable to the product's worth.	3.97	HM	4.40	HM	4.33	HM
5. The price is budget- friendly.	4.00	HM	4.27	HM	4.40	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.15	HM	4.51	VHM	4.49	HM

It can be seen in the Table 27, that the seller and pasalubong store owner respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 60 grams proportion regarding product cost were descriptively rated as “Highly Marketable” (HM), as

evidenced by the mean of 4.15 for sellers and 4.49 for pasalubong store owners, while the consumers rated the product as Very Highly Marketable as indicated in the mean of 4.51. This suggests that the bar cookies are competitive in terms of price, which the respondents found to be marketable. Economical and commensurate with the product's value, making it appealing to the whole market.

Table 28. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion regarding Packaging and Branding

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The brand name is unique.	4.93	VHM	4.83	VHM	4.60	VHM
2. The packaging visually appealing.	4.10	HM	4.53	VHM	4.33	HM
3. The product maintains freshness with its resealable top.	4.00	HM	4.47	HM	4.30	HM
4. The product appears original among another cookie products.	4.10	HM	4.43	HM	4.37	HM
5. The style of the packaging contains appropriate cushioning.	4.27	HM	4.40	HM	4.40	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.28	HM	4.53	VHM	4.40	HM

It can be noted in the table that the seller and pasalubong store owner respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 60 grams proportion regarding packaging and branding were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as showed by weighted mean of 4.28 and 4.40, while the consumers rated the product as Very Highly Marketable as shown in the obtained mean of 4.53. This finding suggests that, in terms of branding and packaging, the product's attractiveness has significantly increased its worth. As a result, this raised brand recognition and encouraged more sales.

Table 29. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 60 Grams Proportion regarding Distribution Channels

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can offer potential partnership	4.80	VHM	4.93	VHM	4.70	VHM
2. The product can deliver the opportunity to reach more people and expand awareness.	4.07	HM	4.50	VHM	4.43	HM
3. The product provides market information to producers.	3.93	HM	4.50	VHM	4.37	HM
4. The product can be easily distributed.	4.30	HM	4.50	VHM	4.43	HM
5. The product can easily establish goals, service, and reporting requirements.	4.13	HM	4.43	HM	4.47	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.25	HM	4.57	VHM	4.48	HM

It can be noted in the table that the seller and pasalubong store owner respondents' assessments on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 60 grams proportion regarding distribution channels were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 4.25 and 4.48, while the consumers rated the product as Very Highly Marketable as revealed in the mean of 4.57.

Table 30. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion regarding Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is capable of supplying the need of potential customers.	4.90	VHM	4.83	VHM	4.63	VHM
2. The product's nutritive content allows it to satiate the requirements of potential customers.	4.17	HM	4.30	HM	4.23	HM
3. The product can be obtained for less than the other comparable high-end brands.	4.13	HM	4.37	HM	4.13	HM
4. Potential customers of various ages can purchase the merchandise.	3.83	HM	4.30	HM	4.10	HM
5. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.27	HM	4.40	HM	4.33	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.26	HM	4.44	HM	4.29	HM

As can be seen from the table, the overall weighted mean of 4.26 for sellers, 4.44 for consumers, and 4.29 for pasalubong store owners indicates that the three groups of respondents' assessments of the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 90 grams

proportion regarding consumer demand were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM). These mean that the product has an organic mechanism that may offer nutritional benefits and that it might fulfill the needs of future consumers. For this reason, they think that requests from customers are legitimate. As a result, there was less need for the product to be valued by consumer want because the market was more likely to benefit from the product's marketability based on customer demand.

Table 31. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion regarding Product Competitiveness

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product offers competitive price.	4.60	VHM	4.73	VHM	4.57	VHM
2. The product is one- of-a-kind.	4.17	HM	4.37	HM	4.27	HM
3. The product offers competitive price range.	4.07	HM	4.33	HM	4.33	HM
4. There are many well-informed buyers of the product.	4.30	HM	4.40	HM	4.47	HM
5. The product can sustain continuous supply and demand of the market.	4.47	HM	4.57	VHM	4.63	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.32	HM	4.48	HM	4.45	HM

The three groups of respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 90 grams proportion regarding product competitiveness were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 4.32 for sellers, 4.48 for consumers and 4.45 for pasalubong store owners. Because of their excellent quality and reasonable pricing, the 90g KaPiliNgka bar cookies are therefore very simple to market. Thus, the product fulfilled and maintained the needs of its customers which made the product a competitive to the target market.

It can be seen in Table 48, that the seller and pasalubong store owner respondents' assessments on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 90 grams proportion regarding product cost were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as shown by the overall weighted mean of 4.32 for sellers and 4.36 for store owners, while the consumer rated the product as Very Highly Marketable as shown in the mean of 4.51.

Table 32. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion regarding Product Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is reasonably priced based on cost.	4.87	VHM	4.70	VHM	4.57	VHM
2. The price is affordable.	4.20	HM	4.53	VHM	4.33	HM
3. The amount is based on product's value.	4.17	HM	4.43	HM	4.20	HM
4. The price is suitable to the product's worth.	3.90	HM	4.37	HM	4.30	HM
5. The price is budget- friendly.	4.47	HM	4.53	VHM	4.40	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.32	HM	4.51	VHM	4.36	HM

Given that the respondents found the bar cookies to be marketable, it appears that they are competitive in terms of price. Economical and appropriate for the product's value, which pleased the market as a whole.

Table 33. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion regarding Packaging and Branding

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The brand name is unique.	4.87	VHM	4.70	VHM	4.60	VHM
2. The packaging visually appealing.	4.23	HM	4.37	HM	4.40	HM
3. The product maintains freshness with its resealable top.	4.13	HM	4.40	HM	4.40	HM
4. The product appears original among other cookie products.	4.13	HM	4.43	HM	4.23	HM
5. The style of the packaging contains appropriate cushioning.	4.20	HM	4.50	VHM	4.37	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.31	HM	4.48	HM	4.40	HM

The three groups of respondents' assessments on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 90 grams proportion regarding packaging and branding were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 4.31 for sellers, 4.48 for consumers and 4.40 for pasalubong store owners. This result indicates that as far as packaging and branding is concerned, attractiveness in the package have added significant value to the product. Thus, this inspired more sales and improved brand

awareness.

Table 34. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies with 90 Grams Proportion regarding Distribution Channels

Indicators	Respondents					
	Sellers		Consumers		Pasalubong Store Owners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can offer potential partnership.	4.73	VHM	4.83	VHM	4.27	VHM
2. The product can deliver the opportunity to reach more people and expand awareness.	4.30	HM	4.43	HM	4.37	HM
3. The product provides market information to producers.	4.23	HM	4.43	HM	4.23	HM
4. The product can be easily distributed.	4.40	HM	4.50	VHM	4.43	HM
5. The product can easily establish goals, service, and reporting requirements.	4.37	HM	4.60	VHM	4.43	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.41	HM	4.56	VHM	4.35	HM

It can be seen in the table that the seller and pasalubong store owner respondents' assessments on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies with 90 grams proportion regarding distribution channels were descriptively rated as "Highly Marketable" (HM), as shown by the overall mean of 4.41 and 4.35, while the consumers rated the product as Very Highly Acceptable with the mean of 4.56.

Test of Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in Three Proportions

Table 35. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in 30 Grams Proportions

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Consumer Demand	6.72	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
b. Product Competitiveness	10.88	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
c. Product Cost	4.86	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
d. Packaging and Branding	5.50	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
e. Distribution Channels	9.37	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant

As shown in the table, there are notable differences between the respondents' assessments of the marketability level of 30 grams of KaPiliNgka bar cookies from sellers, customers, and store owners in terms of consumer demand, product competitiveness, cost, packaging and branding, and distribution channels. These differences are also greater than the critical F value. As a result, there are notable differences in the respondents' assessments.

Table 36. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in 60 Grams Proportions

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Consumer Demand	4.32	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
b. Product Competitiveness	1.96	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
c. Product Cost	8.70	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant
d. Packaging and Branding	2.72	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
e. Distribution Channels	5.92	3.10	Reject the H0	Significant

The table shows that there are significant differences between the respective computed F values, which are above the critical F value, and the assessments made by sellers, consumers, and store owners regarding the marketability level of 60-gram KaPiliNgka bar cookies with respect to consumer demand, product cost, and distribution channels. This supports that the respondents' evaluations are not the same except for product competitiveness, and packaging and branding.

Table 37. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of KaPiliNgka Bar Cookies in 90 Grams Proportions

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Consumer Demand	0.73	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
b. Product Competitiveness	1.08	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
c. Product Cost	1.44	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
d. Packaging and Branding	0.90	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
e. Distribution Channels	1.56	3.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

The table makes it clear that there are no significant differences between the specific computed F values, which are below the critical F value, and the assessments made by sellers, customers, and store owners regarding the marketability level of 90-gram KaPiliNgka bar cookies in terms of consumer demand, product competitiveness, product cost, packaging and branding, and distribution channels. This suggests that the opinions of the respondents are consistent.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Three Groups of Respondents to Further Improve the Product

Comments

1. It's an excellent product that fits the market perfectly. Due to its distinctive ingredients, the majority of the others will undoubtedly surprise the consumer. A bar cookie features a special mixture of Kamias Fruit, Pili Nuts, and Langka Seed that also enhances the flavors of one another.
2. It will be really fascinating to consumers, who will undoubtedly enjoy it. One of their favorite baked goods, cookies, can be eaten with fruit and seeds.
3. These bar cookies are suitable for all age groups, are enticing to eat, have a flavor that is well-balanced, and have the potential to succeed in the market due to their ingredients and distinctive name.
4. The 60grams portion is the most flavorful of the three and has the best appearance, scent, taste, and texture. The three flavors of Kamias, Pili, and Langka are harmoniously combined and complement each other. On the 30gram proportions, it is much sweeter than the two proportions, yet it is still acceptable due to its moist-like feel. In comparison to the other two proportions, the 90 grams portion had the least flavor and was the moistest and sweetest of the three.
5. The cookie bar has a tasty flavor that is distinct. It acts as a gateway for a fresh flavor for the widely available standard bar cookies.
6. A unique name and packaging make the packaging very marketable.

Suggestions:

1. The sugar content may be reduced to make the food more crunch-like.
2. It is suggested to add criteria on the availability of the supply.
3. It is suggested to add a criterion stating that the supply is valued in terms of ingredients.
4. Better if it could be made crunchy outside chewy inside. It needs to be flakier, crunchier and moist-like.
5. The researcher might think about promoting bar cookies as one product in the neighborhood market, pastry store, restaurants, bakery, and pasalubong store owner.
6. Bar cookies' shelf life may be increased by adding additives.

Conclusions

Considering the findings above, the following conclusions are hereby arrived at: The nutritional values and acceptability of the produced KaPiliNgka bar cookies were proven good source of energy based on the physicochemical analysis testing of the product. The KaPiliNgka bar cookies in 30g, 60g, and 90g proportions in terms of appearance, color, aroma, taste, and texture are highly appreciated by the respondents. The respondents have different assessments on the level of acceptability of the product when it comes to appearance and aroma in 30 grams proportion. However, the color, taste, and texture of the product in 30grams proportion doesn't change the way they assessed. More so, in 60 grams proportion, the respondents have diverse assessments as to color while in the aspects of appearance, aroma, taste and texture respondents' assessments do not matter. As to 90grams proportion, the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste and texture does not significant differ. In three proportions, the marketability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies appears to be favorable, as prospective customers would likely support their continued availability in the market. The respondents' evaluation on the marketability of KaPiliNgka bar cookies does not matter in 30 grams proportion. They have significantly differed in assessments of 60 grams proportion in terms of consumer demand, product cost and distribution channels aside from product competitiveness and packaging and branding where no significant differences in their appraisal. Thus, as to 90grams proportion, their evaluation on the marketability level of KaPiliNgka bar cookies does not matter. Based on their experience with the KaPiliNgka bar cookies, the sellers, consumers and pasalubong store owners offered suggestions and comments to improve further the prepared new product innovated by the researcher.

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